

1 **Brewing Public Engagement with Pint of Science USA**

2 Ronan Lordan^{1,*}, Johannes Jahan², Fanny Etienne³, Julien Guillard⁴, John Nguyen⁵, and Claudia
3 Ratti²

4
5 ¹Institute for Translational Medicine and Therapeutics, Perelman School of Medicine, University
6 of Pennsylvania, PA, 19102, USA.

7 ²Department of Physics, University of Houston, Houston, TX 77204, USA.

8 ³David Geffen School of Medicine, Department of Neurology, University of California, Los
9 Angeles, CA, 90095, USA.

10 ⁴Section of Hematology/Oncology, Department of Medicine, Biological Sciences Division, The
11 University of Chicago, Chicago, IL, 60637, USA.

12 ⁵Department of Biology and Biochemistry, University of Houston, Houston, TX 77204, USA.

13 * **Correspondence:** ronanlordanacademic@gmail.com

14
15 **Abstract**

16 Amid complex global challenges and the need for informed public discourse, science outreach is
17 more important than ever. The Pint of Science International Festival, held annually each May,
18 convenes scientists, educators, and philosophers with the public in an informal pub setting to foster
19 dialogue on contemporary scientific topics. Since 2012, it has welcomed over 785,000 attendees
20 across 500 cities in 27 countries. Established in 2014, Pint of Science USA has expanded to 16
21 cities by 2025. This report highlights the festival’s U.S. growth, shares the 2025 National Team’s
22 experiences, and provides a map for future growth in the United States.

23
24 **Keywords:** Science communication; science outreach; Pint of Science; volunteering; science
25 literacy

26
27
28
29
30
31

32 **Introduction**

33 Academic research has undeniably led to technological advances, societal improvements,
34 and greater quality of life in the United States and globally. It is also a major economic driver; every
35 \$1 invested by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) generates \$2.56 in economic activity [1].
36 Publicly funded academic research has underpinned innovations ranging from touch screen
37 technology [2] and Google's search algorithm [3] supported by the National Science Foundation
38 (NSF) or GPS funded by the United States Department of Defense (DOD) [4]. Yet, despite these
39 contributions, academic research is often perceived as detached from public interest or attention
40 [5].

41 Scientists and the public often hold contrasting views on science, evidenced by discussions
42 on climate change, stem cell research or genetically modified foods [6-9]. Misinformation further
43 complicates public understanding, with serious societal consequences, as exemplified during the
44 coronavirus pandemic [10, 11]. In an era of rapid scientific and technological advancement and
45 escalating global challenges, the need for accessible, accurate, and engaging science
46 communication is greater than ever. To bridge the gap between researchers and society, efforts
47 increasingly focus on improving both the communication of scientific findings and the
48 communication skills of the scientists [12-14]. Social media has become a key outlet, reaching
49 broad audiences, encouraging dialogue, and even shaping research for health policy development
50 and initiatives through crowdsourced input [15, 16] or enabling citizen science projects that
51 involve the public in data collection and discussions [17, 18]. Other initiatives have even used
52 comedy as a tool to engage the public with science [19].

53 Pint of Science is an international grassroots non-profit organization that was established
54 in 2012 at Imperial College London in the United Kingdom [20]. This event inspired the idea to
55 bring scientists to the public leading to the inception of the Pint of Science International Festival
56 held in the month of May every year [20]. The Pint of Science festival brings science to venues
57 out of the lab, offering audiences an informal space to engage directly with researchers and the
58 scientific process through short informal talks by scientists from diverse disciplines. Importantly,
59 these events take place in non-traditional settings including pubs, breweries, bars, and cafes [21-
60 23]. These familiar environments lower barriers to participation, attract non-scientist audiences,
61 and humanize the scientists themselves. Within three years and with the support of like-minded
62 scientists, Pint of Science grew into the largest global science outreach festival [23].

63 In this manuscript, we provide our perspectives on the establishment and growth of Pint of
 64 Science in the United States over the last 10 years. We document the establishment and growth of
 65 the organization and the trials and tribulations of running a nationwide organization entirely driven
 66 by volunteers. We speculate what the future holds for Pint of Science USA and why scientists
 67 should engage in scientific outreach.

68
 69 **What is the Pint of Science International Festival?**

70 The Pint of Science International Festival was founded by Dr Michael Motskin and Dr
 71 Praveen Paul, at Imperial College London in the United Kingdom, after a conversation beside a
 72 centrifuge quickly spun out into a plan to bring science to the public [20]. Fueled by a desire to
 73 share their passion to communicate science to the public, they organized a “Meet the Researchers”
 74 event that was held in 2012. Both neuroscientists, they invited people affected by Alzheimer’s
 75 disease, Parkinson’s disease, motor neuron diseases, and multiple sclerosis into the lab to
 76 demonstrate how research in neuroscience is conducted. This inspired the creation of the first
 77 official Pint of Science event taking place in 2013 in the United Kingdom, where events were held
 78 in 15 pubs across London, Oxford, and Cambridge [20]. In 2014, the festival expanded
 79 internationally, with Australia, France, Ireland, Switzerland, and the United States joining. This
 80 was followed by the inclusion of Brazil, Germany, Italy, and Spain in 2015. In the years since, the
 81 festival has continued to grow and now includes chapters in 27 countries in over 500 cities [21]
 82 (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

83 **Figure 1:** The growth of Pint of Science Internationally from 2014 - 2024.

84

85 **Figure 2:** The growth of Pint of Science from 2012-2025. Several countries have been involved
 86 in the festival and not all countries participated all years. In 2025 all 27 countries participated in
 87 the festival.

88

89 The format of Pint of Science has remained largely consistent since it was first devised
 90 [20]. Each May, the festival runs for three consecutive days, with events taking place in multiple
 91 venues spanning various cities. Volunteers at local Pint of Science Chapters coordinate with their
 92 national team to organize events congruently with the International Events. To represent a broad
 93 spectrum of scientific disciplines, events are organized into six core themes encompassing fields
 94 such as biology, chemistry, physics, technology, society, and the environment (Figure 3). In recent
 95 years, there has been a seventh theme added in the U.K. called Creative Reactions, where science
 96 and art are combined to spark a new dimension of science communication [24]. Typically, one
 97 theme is featured per night, with at least two scientists invited to present their research to a public
 98 audience. Presentations are designed to be accessible, interactive, and engaging, often delivered
 99 through slideshow-based talks. Speakers present their research for ~15-20 minutes targeting non-
 100 scientists. This is followed by an informal Q&A session led by the speaker and a member of the

101 local chapter that acts as a master of ceremonies, who encourage audience participation. An
102 intermission between talks provides time to generate further discussion, networking, and informal
103 engagement between presenters and the audience. This break also offers an opportunity to host
104 science-themed activities including pub quizzes or trivia, further enhancing engagement.

105

106

107

108

109

110

111

112

113

114

115

116

117 **Figure 3:** The six core themes of the Pint of Science Festival: Beautiful Mind, Our Society, Planet
118 Earth, Our Body, Tech me Out, and Atoms to Galaxies.

119

120 These events are often sponsored by scientific institutions, universities, or companies that
121 provide funding for advertisement, venue fees, equipment, or science themed merchandise used as
122 trivia prizes or speaker gifts. In some Chapters internationally, sponsors cover core operating costs
123 like the website, while in the U.S. chapters are reliant on charging a \$2 ticket fee to maintain the
124 website, with any surplus reinvested into the following year's festival. In some cases, academic
125 institutions will sponsor the event, in which case equipment and venues may be provided or
126 covered by the university. In many cases in the US, venues provided their establishments for free
127 to support the public outreach efforts.

128

129 **From inception to national growth: Pint of Science USA 2014 - 2025**

130 Pint of Science USA was officially launched in 2014 as part of an international expansion
131 of the Pint of Science Festival. The idea of the original UK festival was simple but powerful: bring

132 scientists out of the lab and into local pubs to share their research directly with the public. In
133 parallel, in Tampa, Florida, scientists Parmvir Bahia and David Basanta, along with Angela Rey
134 and Arturo Araujo, were independently exploring ways to bring science to broader audiences
135 through a monthly podcast. Their efforts culminated in the foundation of the Pint of Science USA
136 Chapter. The first U.S. edition of the festival took place in May 2014, with grassroots events
137 organized in five cities: Chicago, Philadelphia, Tampa, New York City, and San Diego [25]. These
138 inaugural events were fully volunteer-led and operated with minimal infrastructure or centralized
139 support. Yet, from the beginning, the festival attracted the support of local institutions and
140 organizations. In Chicago, for instance, the event was co-hosted by the industry group iBIO,
141 demonstrating that public-private partnerships and corporate interest in science engagement were
142 present from the outset.

143 In 2015, Pint of Science USA expanded significantly, with free events in nine cities:
144 Chicago, Philadelphia, Tampa, New York City, San Diego, San Francisco, Los Angeles, Houston,
145 and Boston/Cambridge [26]. Over the course of three days, the U.S. festival hosted 55 events,
146 covering a broad range of topics from neuroscience and cosmology to environmental science and
147 beer genetics. Corporate and institutional sponsors played an increasingly important role, with
148 support from organizations including New England Biolabs, ThermoFisher Scientific, eLife,
149 Cytoskeleton, Protocols.io, and Tampa Bay Times, among others.

150 The following year, in 2016, the festival grew again, reaching 14 cities including
151 Indianapolis, Knoxville, Research Triangle Park, Miami, and Washington D.C. [27]. Events
152 retained the relaxed pub-based format and continued to emphasize accessibility, community
153 building, and public engagement. That year's festival was supported by sponsors such as
154 ReadCube, and events were praised for their creativity, including musical performances, live
155 demos, and Q&A sessions. In 2017, Pint of Science USA paused its activities. While the reasons
156 were not officially documented, the hiatus likely reflected a transitional period and a loss of
157 leadership from the original U.S. organizing team, which had previously driven much of the
158 grassroots momentum.

159 The festival returned in 2018, though in a more limited format. The official website listed
160 only Baltimore and Portsmouth as host cities, but independent event listings confirm that
161 additional cities such as Pittsburgh and Boston hosted summer editions under the Pint of Science
162 banner [28]. During this time, Nicole Dettmering became the U.S. national director, helping

163 reestablish infrastructure and communication between emerging local chapters. By 2019, the
164 festival had regained momentum, with events in nine cities: San Francisco, Denver, Cincinnati,
165 Pittsburgh, Winston-Salem, Buffalo, New York City, Boston/Cambridge, and Portsmouth [29]. A
166 new national leadership team was formed, including Izabella Pena and Marge Maallo, bringing
167 renewed focus to expansion, branding, and digital outreach.

168 In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic forced the cancellation of in-person events. Initially
169 postponed from May to September, the festival ultimately transitioned to a fully virtual format,
170 with livestreamed talks, global panels, and remote Q&A sessions. Under the direction of Marcus
171 Giron, Pint of Science USA contributed to the global program and adapted to new models of
172 science communication. Despite its success, the festival did not hold U.S. events in 2021, 2022, or
173 2023, marking a temporary halt due to pandemic-related logistical challenges. Internationally,
174 there was a notable drop in the number of events and attendees post COVID-19, but there has also
175 been a resurgence in growth (Figure 4).

176 After a four-year hiatus, Pint of Science USA was successfully revived in 2024. The
177 initiative came from a new national leadership team, composed of the current authors of this article,
178 most of whom had previously participated in Pint of Science events across Europe. Motivated by
179 their past experiences and a shared commitment to public engagement, they independently reached
180 out to Elodie Chabrol, International Director of Pint of Science, and quickly reestablished the U.S.
181 chapter. Despite the short timeframe, the team relaunched the festival in 5 cities across the country,
182 demonstrating both the resilience of the global Pint of Science network and the enduring demand
183 for accessible, community-based science outreach in the United States. In 2025, this grew to 16
184 cities (Figure 5) with many more projected for 2026, marking this third revival as the fastest growth
185 of the festival in the U.S. since the first event.

186

194 **Figure 5:** The growth and revival of Pint of Science USA.

195

196

197

198

199 **Figure 5:** The cities in black denote the 5 cities that took part in the Pint of Science International

200 Festival in 2024 and 2025, and the cities in red denote the cities that joined in 2025.

201 The re-establishment of Pint of Science USA has come with significant challenges, as
202 might be expected with an organization run entirely by volunteers. The growth from 5 cities to 16
203 cities in 2025 required a restructuring of the Pint of Science USA national leadership to delegate
204 regions. This created the positions of the West, East, Midwest, and South coordinators in the
205 national team to delegate leadership and responsibility across several city groups. These regional
206 coordinators communicate with city coordinators to ensure that each city has access to the national
207 resources available such as communication templates, guides for presenters, advertising and
208 branding. The national network is also a source of guidance and troubleshooting. City coordinators
209 work with event managers to run events in each city including recruiting speakers, finding venues,
210 organizing the presentations, providing trivia or related activities to entertain attendees. As it
211 stands, this model works at a national level, but with projected growth over the next few years,
212 additional national coordinators and restructuring may be required. Current coordinators are
213 burdened with multiple roles including communication material design, social media coverage,
214 website maintenance, and sponsorship and treasury activity. Therefore, for future events, more
215 regional and national level roles will be developed to delegate tasks more effectively and to
216 improve the organization's structure.

217 With anticipated growth also draws the challenge of funding and sponsorship. As alluded
218 to Pint of Science USA is highly reliant on sponsorship and \$2 ticket fees to cover the costs of
219 hosting the website (www.pintofscience.us) and other operating costs. In lieu of cash donations,
220 some sponsoring organizations pay venue fees or purchase advertising/branding materials on
221 behalf of Pint of Science for the hosted events. Other sponsors provide prizes for trivia. However,
222 this is an unsustainable model moving forward, as it was already a limitation to get sponsorship
223 from certain organizations that would only make transfers to a non-profit organization (NPO) with
224 a legal status. Considering the potential expansion of Pint of Science in the United States,
225 sustainable growth will require the organization to seek 501(c)(3) NPO status to receive monetary
226 sponsorships that will allow for equal distribution of resources across the country. This will be
227 challenging due to the volunteer nature of the organization; hence legal support will be required.
228 However, other Pint of Science chapters have managed similar processes, including Ireland who
229 have successfully registered the organization as a registered charity .

230

231 **International Scholars as a driving force for Pint of Science USA**

232 Since its inception, Pint of Science USA has been deeply shaped by the contributions of
233 international scholars, particularly early-career researchers and postdoctoral fellows who bring
234 with them prior experience from other national chapters. These scholars have not only filled critical
235 organizational roles but have also been instrumental in transplanting the cultural DNA of Pint of
236 Science into the American science communication landscape consistent with broader evidence that
237 internationally mobile scientists act as knowledge transmitters across borders [30, 31].

238 Many members of the current national team, including the authors of this paper, first
239 encountered Pint of Science while living or studying in Europe. Familiar with the festival's format,
240 philosophy, and impact, they carried that experience with them when moving to the United States
241 for research. In the absence of a robust science communication infrastructure at many U.S.
242 institutions, Pint of Science became a vehicle for these scholars to stay connected to public
243 engagement and to bring a tested model of outreach into their new academic environments.

244 This dynamic is not unique to the current leadership. Throughout its history, Pint of Science
245 U.S. has benefited from the energy, cross-cultural perspective, and organizational initiative of non-
246 U.S. born scientists as demonstrated by the membership of the organization from events managers
247 to national leaders. The original U.S. chapter itself was co-founded by Parmvir Bahia and David
248 Basanta, both of whom had international academic backgrounds and ties to the global Pint of
249 Science network. In later years, city coordinators and volunteers frequently included researchers
250 from France, Brazil, Ireland, Germany, the U.K. and other countries with many active Pint of
251 Science Chapters.

252 This steady influx of globally minded scholars has had several benefits. First, it has ensured
253 that the U.S. festival remains strongly tied to the international Pint of Science identity, maintaining
254 consistency in branding, tone, and quality. Second, it has helped foster a spirit of collaboration
255 across borders and disciplines, often leading to events that blend local scientific expertise with
256 global perspectives. Finally, it has highlighted the value of immigrant and visiting scholars not just
257 as researchers, but as public ambassadors of science.

258 However, this dependence on international volunteers also poses structural challenges. In
259 2023, 57.9% of U.S. postdocs were on temporary visas [32] and faced intense academic pressures,
260 making sustained involvement difficult as evidenced by the stop start nature of the early years of
261 Pint of Science US [33]. Additionally, their outsider status can limit institutional access or support.

262 These issues underscore the need for institutional recognition and support of science
263 communication work, especially for scholars who take on these roles despite precarious
264 employment or limited time [33].

265

266 **Why should scientists get involved in science communication and Pint of Science?**

267 It is increasingly important for scientists to engage with their local communities to share
268 their expertise and foster trust, especially as the PEW Research Center data shows declining
269 confidence in scientists. In 2019 indicated that 54% of respondents thought scientists were good
270 communicators, but by 2024, only 45% of respondents perceived scientists this way. Additionally,
271 more respondents in 2024 perceive scientists as feeling superior to others (47%, up 4%), cold
272 (34%, up 5%), closed-minded (28%, up 2%), and that they don't pay attention to the moral values
273 of society (36%, up 4%) [34]. Participating in science communication initiatives can help to
274 demystify research and academia for the public [35], potentially reducing distrust of the scientific
275 community and dismantling perceived barriers between researchers and the public. Engagement is
276 particularly important in times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic [23, 36], when public
277 understanding and trust in science is vital at both societal and political levels.

278 Outreach programs can improve scientific literacy and trust [37] and are demonstratively
279 effective [38-40], though they are mostly school-focused, leaving fewer opportunities for adults
280 [41, 42]. Initiatives like Pint of Science address this gap by targeting adult audiences with
281 interactive discussion and science themed communication. Beyond formal programs, sharing
282 research through social media or non-academic channels can raise public awareness, foster
283 scientific collaboration, and provide career benefits such as increased visibility, citations, media
284 coverage, and potential funding opportunities [43-48].

285 Despite these benefits, participation in science outreach remains low among scientists [49,
286 50]. While many scientists value education and outreach, they encounter barriers including limited
287 institutional support, competing research demands, and challenges in communicating with non-
288 scientific audiences [42]. The national Pint of Science organization helps address these obstacles
289 by supporting local chapters with resources, guidance, and connections to experienced scientific
290 communicators. Pint of Science events provide researchers with the opportunity to gain valuable
291 communication and leadership skills, notably by offering support material such as written guides,
292 training, and mentorship. For example, International Pint of Science Director Élodie Chabrol

293 offers targeted training to help researchers gain skills to present effectively to public audiences.
294 The wider international network including the Director is also available to guide national teams
295 on organization and communication.

296 Outreach activities can also amplify research impact by increasing visibility and
297 encouraging participation in studies and clinical trials [51]. Although some perceive outreach as a
298 distraction from research, evidence suggests it is associated with better research performance [52].
299 Nevertheless, limited institutional support remains an impediment for many academics [42]. Pint
300 of Science further benefits researchers by fostering interdisciplinary connections. For instance, at
301 the 2025 Philadelphia Pint of Science Festival, researchers from five universities (Drexel
302 University, Jefferson University, Princeton University, the University of Pennsylvania, and Rowan
303 University) shared insights spanning medicine, biomedical sciences, neuroscience, astrophysics,
304 brewing science, and artificial intelligence. These rare interactions create opportunities for
305 collaborations that might not otherwise occur.

306 Pint of Science is a volunteer-driven, non-profit grassroots movement with multiple
307 pathways to get involved in the United States and globally (Figure 6). Opportunities to support
308 Pint of Science are available at various levels of leadership and engagement. Regardless of the
309 role, getting involved not only helps to sustain the Pint of Science festival but also provides
310 meaningful opportunities for community members and scientists to foster practical skills in public
311 engagement, teamwork, and scientific communication. Although barriers such as limited time and
312 funding evidently persist [53], Pint of Science helps lower these obstacles by providing structured
313 outreach opportunities and a supportive global network of scientists.

314

315

316 **Figure 6:** Science communication is critical to societal advancement. No matter where you are in
 317 the world, you can get involved in the Pint of Science International movement by attending events,
 318 presenting your research at events, joining or establishing a local chapter, or sponsoring an event.

319

320 **Acknowledgements**

321 We would like to acknowledge the volunteers across the International Pint of Science Organization
 322 and the City Coordinators and Event Managers in the 16 cities across the United States for their
 323 time and effort running these events. We also appreciate the speakers and venues across the country
 324 for their support hosting these events. Critically, we would like to thank the public who engage
 325 with Pint of Science and attend these events. We would like to thank our national and local
 326 sponsors over the years, and we would like to thank The UCLA Brain Research Institute, The
 327 University of Houston College of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, The University of Houston
 328 Department of Physics, Rockland Immunochemicals (Antibodies Online), Philosophical
 329 Magazine, and Giant Microbes Inc. for their support of the 2025 events. We also acknowledge the
 330 support of the International Pint of Science Organization alongside Dr Élodie Chabrol and Dr
 331 Praveen Paul.

332

333

334 **Conflicts of Interest**

335 The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare. All authors are volunteers with Pint of Science
336 USA.

337

338 **References**

- 339 1. United for Medical Research. *NIH'S Role in Sustaining the U.S. Economy*. 2025 [cited
340 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://www.unitedformedicalresearch.org/wp-](https://www.unitedformedicalresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/UMR_NIH-Role-in-Sustaining-US-Economy-FY2024-2025-Update.pdf)
341 [content/uploads/2025/03/UMR_NIH-Role-in-Sustaining-US-Economy-FY2024-2025-](https://www.unitedformedicalresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/UMR_NIH-Role-in-Sustaining-US-Economy-FY2024-2025-Update.pdf)
342 [Update.pdf](https://www.unitedformedicalresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/UMR_NIH-Role-in-Sustaining-US-Economy-FY2024-2025-Update.pdf).
- 343 2. U.S. National Science Foundation. *Pocket-sized progress: Smartphones and NSF*
344 *innovations*. 2025 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://www.nsf.gov/science-](https://www.nsf.gov/science-matters/pocket-sized-progress-smartphones-nsf-innovations)
345 [matters/pocket-sized-progress-smartphones-nsf-innovations](https://www.nsf.gov/science-matters/pocket-sized-progress-smartphones-nsf-innovations).
- 346 3. U.S. National Science Foundation. *On the Origins of Google*. 2025 [cited 2025 Sep 2];
347 Available from: <https://www.nsf.gov/news/origins-google>.
- 348 4. Juncu, K. and M. Livaudais, *An Analysis of the GPS R&D Program as a case study*
349 *illustrating DOD R&D and its associated successes to justify the continued investments*
350 *into sustainment of DOD R7D budgets*. 2016.
- 351 5. Rouzer, S.K., L.M. Kalinowski, and E.T. Kaseda, *The importance of promoting scientific*
352 *advocacy & outreach for trainees*. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 2023. **48**(5): p. 713-715.
- 353 6. NPR. *Scientists, General Public Have Divergent Views On Science, Report Says*. 2015
354 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-](https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-)
355 [way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-](https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-)
356 [report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-](https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-)
357 [.Scientists%2C%20General%20Public%20Have%20Divergent%20Views%20On%20Sci](https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-)
358 [ence%2C%20Report%20Says,climate%20change%20and%20human%20evolution](https://www.npr.org/sections/thetwo-way/2015/01/29/382464912/scientists-general-public-have-divergent-views-on-science-report-says#:~:text=Hourly%20News-).
- 359 7. Pew Research Center. *Public and Scientists' Views on Science and Society*. 2015 [cited
360 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2015/01/29/public-](https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2015/01/29/public-and-scientists-views-on-science-and-society/)
361 [and-scientists-views-on-science-and-society/](https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2015/01/29/public-and-scientists-views-on-science-and-society/).
- 362 8. Kahan, D.M., et al., *The polarizing impact of science literacy and numeracy on perceived*
363 *climate change risks*. *Nature climate change*, 2012. **2**(10): p. 732-735.
- 364 9. Allum, N., et al., *Religious beliefs, knowledge about science and attitudes towards medical*
365 *genetics*. *Public Understanding of Science*, 2014. **23**(7): p. 833-849.
- 366 10. The Lancet Infectious, D., *The COVID-19 infodemic*. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*,
367 2020. **20**(8): p. 875.
- 368 11. Cuan-Baltazar, J.Y., et al., *Misinformation of COVID-19 on the Internet: Infodemiology*
369 *Study*. *JMIR Public Health Surveill*, 2020. **6**(2): p. e18444.
- 370 12. Bautista, C., et al., *Ten simple rules for improving communication among scientists*. *PLoS*
371 *Comput Biol*, 2022. **18**(6): p. e1010130.
- 372 13. Scalice, D., et al., *FameLab USA: Improving Science Communication Skills for Early*
373 *Career Scientists*. *Astrobiology*, 2019. **19**(4): p. 614-623.
- 374 14. Greer, S., et al., *The Art of Science Communication—A Novel Approach to Science*
375 *Communication Training*. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education*, 2018.
376 **19**(1): p. 10.1128/jmbe.v19i1.1547.

- 377 15. Mondal, H., et al., *Twitter-based crowdsourcing: What kind of measures can help to end*
378 *the COVID-19 pandemic faster?* *Frontiers in Medicine*, 2022. **9**.
- 379 16. Saeed, M., et al., *Crowdsourced Fact-Checking at Twitter: How Does the Crowd Compare*
380 *With Experts?*, in *Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Information*
381 *& Knowledge Management*. 2022, Association for Computing Machinery: Atlanta, GA,
382 USA. p. 1736–1746.
- 383 17. Daume, S. and V. Galaz, “*Anyone Know What Species This Is?*” – *Twitter Conversations*
384 *as Embryonic Citizen Science Communities*. *PLOS ONE*, 2016. **11**(3): p. e0151387.
- 385 18. Edwards, T., et al., *Passive citizen science: The role of social media in wildlife*
386 *observations*. *PLOS ONE*, 2021. **16**(8): p. e0255416.
- 387 19. Roche, J., et al., *Bright Club: Establishing a Science Comedy Variety Night in Ireland*.
388 *Science Communication*, 2020. **42**(1): p. 130-140.
- 389 20. Paul, P. and M. Motskin, *Engaging the Public with Your Research*. *Trends in Immunology*,
390 2016. **37**(4): p. 268-271.
- 391 21. Pint of Science U.S. *Pint of Science U.S. About*. 2025 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from:
392 <https://pintofscience.us/about/>.
- 393 22. Richter, K. and N. Thomas, *Science in the Eye of the Beer-Holder—How To Put On an*
394 *Effective Pint of Science: The Adelaide Experience*. *Journal of Microbiology &*
395 *Biology Education*, 2018. **19**(1): p. 10.1128/jmbe.v19i1.1539.
- 396 23. Robinson, M.T., et al., *The First Pint of Science Festival in Asia*. *Science Communication*,
397 2017. **39**(6): p. 810-820.
- 398 24. U.K., P.o.S. *Pint of Science: Creative Reactions*. 2022 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from:
399 <https://pintofscience.co.uk/creativereactions/>.
- 400 25. UIC Today. *Join UIC researchers in a Pint of Science at local tavern*. 2014 [cited 2025
401 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://today.uic.edu/join-uic-researchers-in-a-pint-of-science-at-](https://today.uic.edu/join-uic-researchers-in-a-pint-of-science-at-local-tavern/)
402 [local-tavern/](https://today.uic.edu/join-uic-researchers-in-a-pint-of-science-at-local-tavern/).
- 403 26. NPR: WUSF BBC Newshour. *Science and Suds Meet at Sold-Out 'Pint of Science' Events*.
404 2015 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://www.wusf.org/university-beat/2015-05-](https://www.wusf.org/university-beat/2015-05-18/science-and-suds-meet-at-sold-out-pint-of-science-events)
405 [18/science-and-suds-meet-at-sold-out-pint-of-science-events](https://www.wusf.org/university-beat/2015-05-18/science-and-suds-meet-at-sold-out-pint-of-science-events).
- 406 27. The BMS Times. *Pint of Science Festival: Bringing Scientists to a Pub Near You*. 2016
407 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from: [https://thebmstimes.wordpress.com/2016/06/20/pint-](https://thebmstimes.wordpress.com/2016/06/20/pint-of-science-festival-bringing-scientists-to-a-pub-near-you/)
408 [of-science-festival-bringing-scientists-to-a-pub-near-you/](https://thebmstimes.wordpress.com/2016/06/20/pint-of-science-festival-bringing-scientists-to-a-pub-near-you/).
- 409 28. The Boston Calendar. *Science by the Pint @ Aeronaut Brewery*. 2018 [cited 2025 Sep 2];
410 Available from: [https://www.thebostoncalendar.com/events/science-by-the-pint-aeronaut-](https://www.thebostoncalendar.com/events/science-by-the-pint-aeronaut-brewery--4)
411 [brewery--4](https://www.thebostoncalendar.com/events/science-by-the-pint-aeronaut-brewery--4).
- 412 29. NPR: Short Wave. *2020 Pint Of Science Festival Will Be Virtual Because Of COVID-19*.
413 2020 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from:
414 [https://www.npr.org/2020/09/07/910399204/2020-pint-of-science-festival-will-be-](https://www.npr.org/2020/09/07/910399204/2020-pint-of-science-festival-will-be-virtual-because-of-covid-19)
415 [virtual-because-of-covid-19](https://www.npr.org/2020/09/07/910399204/2020-pint-of-science-festival-will-be-virtual-because-of-covid-19).
- 416 30. Aman, V., *Internationally mobile scientists as knowledge transmitters: A lexical-based*
417 *approach to detect knowledge transfer*. *Journal of the Association for Information Science*
418 *and Technology*, 2022. **73**(10): p. 1418-1431.
- 419 31. Aman, V., *Transfer of knowledge through international scientific mobility: Introduction of*
420 *a network-based bibliometric approach to study different knowledge types*. *Quantitative*
421 *Science Studies*, 2020. **1**(2): p. 565-581.

- 422 32. Smith, B., et al., *National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics (NCSES):*
423 *Graduate Enrollment and Postdoctoral Appointments in Science, Engineering, and Health*
424 *Rise, Driven Largely by Increases in the Number of Women and Temporary Visa Holders.*
425 2024.
- 426 33. Kahn, S. and M. MacGarvie, *New evidence on international postdocs in the US: Less pay,*
427 *different experiences.* Research Policy, 2024. **53**(9): p. 105077.
- 428 34. Pew Research Center. *Public Trust in Scientists and Views on Their Role in Policymaking.*
429 2024 [cited 2025 Sep 2]; Available from:
430 [https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2024/11/14/public-trust-in-scientists-and-views-on-](https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2024/11/14/public-trust-in-scientists-and-views-on-their-role-in-policymaking/)
431 [their-role-in-policymaking/](https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2024/11/14/public-trust-in-scientists-and-views-on-their-role-in-policymaking/).
- 432 35. Jucan, M.S. and C.N. Jucan, *The Power of Science Communication.* Procedia - Social and
433 Behavioral Sciences, 2014. **149**: p. 461-466.
- 434 36. Goldstein, C.M., et al., *Science Communication in the Age of Misinformation.* Annals of
435 Behavioral Medicine, 2021. **54**(12): p. 985-990.
- 436 37. Friedman, D.P., *Public Outreach: A Scientific Imperative.* The Journal of Neuroscience,
437 2008. **28**(46): p. 11743-11745.
- 438 38. DeWaters, J. and S. Powers, *Improving Science Literacy Through Project Based K 12*
439 *Outreach Efforts That Use Energy And Environmental Themes.* 2006 Annual Conference
440 & Exposition, 2006: p. 11-738.
- 441 39. Arthur, B., et al., *Ocean Outreach in Australia: How a National Research Facility is*
442 *Engaging with Community to Improve Scientific Literacy.* Frontiers in Environmental
443 Science, 2021. **Volume 9 - 2021**.
- 444 40. Tuttle, M.J., et al., *Promoting Science Literacy and Awareness across the Globe: the Role*
445 *of Scientists as Science Ambassadors.* Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education,
446 2023. **24**(2): p. e00041-23.
- 447 41. Gagnon, N.L. and A.J. Komor, *Addressing an Overlooked Science Outreach Audience:*
448 *Development of a Science Mentorship Program Focusing on Critical Thinking Skills for*
449 *Adults Working toward a High School Equivalency Degree.* Journal of Chemical
450 Education, 2017. **94**(10): p. 1435-1442.
- 451 42. McCann, B.M., C.B. Cramer, and L.G. Taylor, *Assessing the impact of education and*
452 *outreach activities on research scientists.* Journal of Higher Education Outreach and
453 Engagement, 2015. **19**(1): p. 65-78.
- 454 43. Ravinetto, R. and J.A. Singh, *Responsible dissemination of health and medical research:*
455 *some guidance points.* BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine, 2023. **28**(3): p. 144-147.
- 456 44. Özkent, Y., *Social media usage to share information in communication journals: An*
457 *analysis of social media activity and article citations.* PLOS ONE, 2022. **17**(2): p.
458 e0263725.
- 459 45. Paradis, N., et al., *Twitter: A Platform for Dissemination and Discussion of Scientific*
460 *Papers in Radiation Oncology.* Am J Clin Oncol, 2020. **43**(6): p. 442-445.
- 461 46. Hassan, S.-U., et al., *Introducing the 'alt-index' for measuring the social visibility of*
462 *scientific research.* Scientometrics, 2020. **123**(3): p. 1407-1419.
- 463 47. Mueller-Herbst, J.M., et al., *Saw It on Facebook: The Role of Social Media in Facilitating*
464 *Science Issue Awareness.* Social Media + Society, 2020. **6**(2): p. 2056305120930412.
- 465 48. McClain, C. and L. Neeley, *A critical evaluation of science outreach via social media: its*
466 *role and impact on scientists [version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with*
467 *reservations]*. F1000Research, 2015. **3**(300).

- 468 49. Varner, J., *Scientific Outreach: Toward Effective Public Engagement with Biological*
469 *Science*. *BioScience*, 2014. **64**(4): p. 333-340.
- 470 50. Rust, N.C., *The unexpected value of communicating science to the public*. *Nature Reviews*
471 *Neuroscience*, 2025: p. 1-2.
- 472 51. Bardach, S.H., et al., *The Effectiveness of Community-based Outreach Events for the*
473 *Promotion of African American Research Participation*. *Alzheimer Dis Assoc Disord*,
474 2020. **34**(4): p. 344-349.
- 475 52. Kassab, O., *Does public outreach impede research performance? Exploring the*
476 *'researcher's dilemma' in a sustainability research center*. *Science and Public Policy*,
477 2019. **46**(5): p. 710-720.
- 478 53. Woitowich, N.C., et al., *Assessing motivations and barriers to science outreach within*
479 *academic science research settings: A mixed-methods survey*. *Frontiers in Communication*,
480 2022. **Volume 7 - 2022**.
- 481